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TRANSLATION OF WORKS FOR BANDURA

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The article highlights the theoretical and practical aspects of the translation of musical works for bandura, which is an important part of modern bandura art. The main trends in the translation of works of various genres and styles are considered, focusing on preserving the authenticity of the original and adapting it to the capabilities of the bandura. The specifics of the repertoire policy are revealed, which contributes to the expansion of the concert and pedagogical repertoire for the instrument. The work explores the pedagogical tasks of translating works for art educational institutions, in particular the formation of technical and artistic skills of students. An analysis of the translation of works by Ukrainian composers M. Lysenko, M. Lyudkevych, A. Vakhnianyn, M. Dremluga, I. Karabyts is carried out in order to determine their contribution to the development of bandura performance. The methodological principles of translation are separately considered, in particular the influence of genre, style and technical features of original works on the process of adaptation for bandura. Based on the analysis of literature and practical experience, recommendations are proposed for composers and performers that will contribute to the further development of the bandura as an academic instrument.

Key words: bandura, arrangements of works, Ukrainian music, pedagogical repertoire, instrumental art, adaptation.

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EFFECTIVE WAYS AND METHODS OF TEACHING ENGLISH IN PRIMARY GRADES

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Due to the fact that our education is aimed at entering the global educational space, significant attention is paid to the issues of teaching foreign languages, especially updating the goals, content, principles, means and methods. From this point of view, the urgent task is considered to be the study and application of a new model of teaching and technologies of teaching a foreign language as a socially developing subject. In the conditions when the world is going through a powerful process of globalization and integration, the task of education is not only to prepare talented youth, but also to form them

into individuals who meet the demands of the time. The development of the personality of the modern era with the help of traditional education and training does not achieve the goal. The development of a perfect person is measured not by his memory, but by the development of his thinking. From this point of view, the article studies and summarizes the school experience of teaching English in elementary grades.

At the stage of development of modern society, modernization of education in Azerbaijan is associated with the use of innovative processes in the organization of foreign languages. Today, the focus is on the student, his personality and unique inner world. That is why in the learning process it is necessary to choose appropriate optimal methods and forms aimed at developing the personality. In recent years, new teaching technologies have been used in English lessons in elementary grades. This is also teaching new forms and methods, that is, a new approach to the learning process.

Thus, the main goal of teaching English in elementary grades is to form a student's communicative culture, develop personality and practical mastery of a foreign language. Its main task is to develop the basics of students' communicative and developmental competencies. However, this task involves the formation of not only practical skills in students, but also certain personal qualities: raising students to be sociable, independent thinkers, capable of making decisions, inclined to establish communicative relationships with friends. The concept of the activity principle implies such activity that is characterized by a high level of motivation, transformation of knowledge and skills into demand, focus on results and compliance with social norms.

Key words: primary school, foreign language teaching, communicative competence, learning process, students.

The main participants in communicative-developmental education are teachers and students, and the goal of communicative-developmental education is considered to be the formation of relevant competencies in students through appropriate games and activities. Communicative-developmental competence is a set of knowledge and skills that provide personal characteristics and capabilities of a person. When teaching a foreign language, the following components of communicative competence are distinguished:

- linguistic competence – the formation of a certain volume of formal knowledge and, accordingly, skills related to various aspects of language (phonetics, vocabulary, grammar);
- sociolinguistic competence – the ability of the speaker to choose linguistic forms depending on the communicative context;
- socio-cultural competence – the ability to acquire knowledge about the norms of social etiquette, national mentality, cultural values;
- discursive competence – the ability to express one's opinion in a foreign language at a level understandable to the interviewee;
- strategic competence – the ability to use communication strategies (verbal and non-verbal). When designing a system of classes that play an important role in the development of communicative activity in a foreign language, it is necessary to take into account the nature of habits and skills that constitute the main components of human activity [3].

One of the most important activities in teaching a foreign language in elementary grades is listening and understanding. Since listening and understanding are the most important activities in teaching a foreign language in elementary grades, its teaching is closely linked to other speech activities and creates the basis for speaking.

Listening comprehension, which plays a key role in the development of foreign speech, involves developing students' ability to listen attentively to expressions they hear, understand their content, and memorize newly learned information. The development of speech in a foreign language is associated with the development of skills and abilities.

The acquisition of listening skills is carried out using various methods. For example, in the process of playing CD s and conducting phonetic exercises, students select words and sentences by listening and repeating sounds, and try to correctly identify the accent. The teacher's work on live examples, pictures, models, illustrations and slides arouses students' interest in the English language, and they correctly select images related to the topic. Speaking in monologue and dialogic form ensures the correct choice of words, involvement in communication and correct expression of thoughts. To do this, the teacher must create a motive, provide children with situations for communication. In this process, children can express their opinion in the form of confirmation or denial. To do this, it is necessary to have a sufficient number of words and phrases in the vocabulary. Of great importance is the methods used by the teacher in communicative language teaching. When teaching foreign languages, words are not given separately, but by topic. That is, words and phrases are given around the topic, and a connection with previous topics is ensured. The words learned must be implemented in speech. Teaching words and phrases with the help of pictures is also of great importance [1].

In teaching a foreign language, grammar is one of the means of learning the language. Grammar is taught in the communicative aspect together with the language itself.

One of the most important activities in teaching foreign languages in elementary grades is reading. During reading, students master basic reading skills, construct narrative and interrogative sentences, highlight new words and information in the text they read, and understand the meaning of these words in accordance with the content.

In order to understand what they read, students are given explanations of the meaning of unfamiliar words before reading the text. Another important activity is writing. Since writing enriches the communicative function of language, it also plays an important role in expanding its sphere of influence.

Written speech is a type of educational activity during which students develop not only some skills and abilities, but also the process of forming the child's personality. The role of games in developing the listed skills in students should be especially noted. Special games organized during the lesson increase students' interest in the lesson and make them more active [2].

Organization and methods of teaching foreign language at the primary level of education. In modern times, the need of people for communication in various spheres is increasing. At present, it is impossible to communicate without acquiring such effective skills as oral and written speech in a foreign language. Therefore, the organization and methods of teaching a foreign language at the primary level of education should serve this purpose. The effectiveness of the process of teaching a foreign language, the activities of teachers and students and, finally, the achievement of learning goals depend on the forms of organization of training, the methods and technologies used, as well as the means. Forms of organization of training influence the volume of knowledge, skills and abilities of students, conscious assimilation of material, development of independent and creative activity, increasing the educational role of training.

In accordance with the requirements of modern education, when choosing forms, techniques and methods of teaching, it is necessary to take into account the following criteria:

- creation of a favorable environment for independent creativity of the student, stimulation of his interests;
- respect for the personality of students, their emotions, feelings and development of their creative abilities;
- ensuring the activity of students, considering it as the main aspect of the educational process;
- the teacher acts as a guide in the educational process;
- teaching primary school students independent work in English at the level of their physical, intellectual and emotional capabilities, or more precisely ensuring differentiation and individualization of the learning process;
- using various forms of work in the lesson: individual, group, collective, independent, stimulating activity, work that develops creative abilities.

The choice of one or another form of work depends on the topic being studied and the purpose of the lesson. The teacher can choose several forms of work when presenting any topic. If the chosen form of work is individual, the teacher should prepare a question or task for each student separately, if he plans to organize work in pairs or different groups, he should keep in mind the following:

- students should have developed teamwork skills;
- they should be given real conditions for communicating with each other and exchanging ideas;
- students should be shown how to solve problems together;
- the ability to assess the level of others should be instilled.
- the ability to respect the opinions of others should be developed.

The importance of games in the process of interactive learning is great. Games change the content of foreign language learning at the initial level:

- ✓ authentically presents a foreign language to students;
- ✓ develops students' critical thinking;
- ✓ increases motivation, creates interest in using the language;
- ✓ increases students' independence and self-confidence;
- ✓ ensures that a tedious lesson is replaced by an interesting and fun one;
- ✓ facilitates the learning process, strengthens memory. The listed factors ensure developmental learning [4].

In the research process, foreign language classes were aimed at the free activity of students and created the opportunity to learn the language through communication. Students acquire free speech skills, using words and expressions in English in role-playing games, situations, scenes.

A teacher who will teach a foreign language at the primary level must be able to:

- teach a foreign language using interactive methods;
- develop receptive, productive and other skills of students;
- present individual grammatical language materials as part of the relevant language materials;
- organize a lesson in accordance with modern standards and with high quality;
- conduct classes in a foreign language (if necessary, using the native language);
- use of auxiliary and technological means in the lesson;
- listen attentively to students, correct mistakes or make additions, intervening only when necessary;

- develop students' communication and observation skills;
- achieve students' fluency in using language units in various situations;
- achieve students' instilling such skills as selection, study and use.

Thus, the foundations of using a foreign language as a means of communication are laid from the junior classes. During this period, if they explain their thoughts in an unfamiliar situation, read and understand any simple text, participate in role-playing games, they can easily continue this work in senior classes. At this stage, students must communicate using simple speech designations in accordance with their interests, know the names of objects that they encounter in everyday life, distinguish and pronounce various sounds of the foreign language being studied compared to their native language, and learn the skills of explaining their content by reading short texts. During this period, they simultaneously develop basic writing skills.

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ЕФЕКТИВНІ СПОСОБИ І МЕТОДИ НАВЧАННЯ АНГЛІЙСЬКОЇ МОВИ В ПОЧАТКОВИХ КЛАСАХ

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У зв'язку з тим, що освіта Азербайджану спрямована на вихід у світовий освітній простір, питанням навчання іноземних мов, особливо оновленню цілей, змісту, принципів, засобів та методів приділяється значна увага. З цієї точки зору актуальним завданням вважається дослідження та застосування нової моделі навчання та технологій викладання іноземної мови як соціально розвивається. В умовах, коли світ переживає потужний процес глобалізації та інтеграції, завдання освіти полягає не лише у підготовці здібної молоді, а й у формуванні з неї осіб, які відповідають вимогам часу.

На етапі розвитку сучасного суспільства модернізація освіти в Азербайджані пов'язана із застосуванням інноваційних процесів в організації іноземної мови. Сьогодні в центрі уваги стоїть учень, його особистість та унікальний внутрішній світ. В останні роки на уроках англійської початкових класів застосовуються нові технології навчання. Це також навчання нових форм і методів, тобто нового підходу до процесу навчання.

Таким чином, основною метою навчання англійської мови у початкових класах є формування комунікативної культури школяра, розвиток особистості та практичне оволодіння іноземною мовою. Його основне завдання – розвиток основ комунікативних та розвиваючих компетенцій учнів. Проте це завдання передбачає формування в учнів як практичних навичок, а й певних якостей особистості: виховання учнів товариськими, самостійними, незалежними мислителями, здатних ухвалювати рішення, схильних до встановлення комунікативних відносин із друзями. Поняття принципу активності передбачає таку діяльність, яка характеризує високий рівень мотивації, трансформацію знань та умінь у затребуваність, орієнтованість на результат та відповідність соціальним нормам. Аналізуються прийоми та форми, спрямовані на формування високої мотиваційної складової у навчальному процесі.

Ключові слова: початкові класи, навчання іноземної мови, комунікативна компетентність, мотивація, навчання, учні.

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ACTIVE POSITION AS AN IMPORTANT FACTOR IN PUPILS ACQUIRING AN ACTIVE CIVIC STANCE

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